

Patterns of emergence: musical form over feedback

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Abstract

This experimental research seeks music structuring strategies in theories of emergence, through which a theoretical framework based on patterns of emergence has been developed as guideline for performing and modelling audible ecosystems. Our methodological approach considers micro and macro level at once, where abstract patterns of emergent structures and feedback topology come as support for an analytical listening and technical implementation. At the micro level, we are dealing with a taxonomy of emergence based on feedback topologies and with causal correlations, looking forward to mapping an operational field behind the interactions. At the macro level, where the sound events are, we are supported by a typology of dynamics for categorizing emergent structures. In other words, our approach is centered on the *quality of the interactions* by which sounds take form. This theoretical framework is one of the *Ecos Study* outcomes, and we believe that it can be improved complementarily with other theories of the electroacoustic field.

1. Introduction

The growth of creative practices involving acoustic feedback have indicated new ways to think about musical processes in both operational and experiential senses (VAN ECK, 2017). Our hypothesis of structural model lies in specific works that use signals controlled positive feedback to integrate acoustic, analog and digital environments as parts of the musical ecosystem (WATERS, 2007). In this sense, the Audible Ecosystem paradigm (DI SCIPIO, 2003) has offered an open field to artistic and technological research. On this matter, the *Ecos Study* has been developed finding control strategies to enable an eco-systemic perspective of musical performance based on patterns of emergence (THOMASI & FARIA, 2022). In this paper, we show the rationale involved in the *Ecos* experiments. We believe that this approach points to possibilities for new models of thinking about musical organisation in complex contexts.

2. The patterns of emergence

Jones (2002), has appointed five main characteristics of emergent structures: *a) novelty*, some new event or organization of the elements; *b) unpredictability* of their properties; *c) coherence or integrity*, when they are held together by causal interactions that constitute their organic unit; *d) self-maintenance*, a contingent stability with respect to variations in the environment; and *e) causal asymmetry*, with respect an emergence of novel causal properties. Those characteristics

can be more or less perceived according to the strength that the phenomenon exhibits. So, according to Jones, emergent structures are dependent on *organizing relations*.

Considering the emergence as a structural factor of music organization proposes a perspective centered on the complexity that involves the sound structures, which embraces layers of different natures and complexity levels. On the one hand, it can be related to the idea of event, regarding sonic experience status (KENDALL, 2008). On the other hand, granular approaches seek to recover the ontological status of the emergence production by converting the micro-level structures into symbolic-operators (VAGGIONE, 2008), or even by creating the micro-level relationships — what Di Scipio called *composing interactions* (DI SCIPIO, 2003). Anyway, we are faced with the first big challenge when dealing with the emergence concept: the complexity that gives it strength is the same that makes it vague. So, how can we deal with the emergent structures in a more objective way?

According to Winning and Bechtel (2019), it is necessary to distinguish between the concept of *Being Emergence* from *Pattern Emergence*. While the former is strongly related to the existence of the phenomenon itself and to its ontological relation with its elements, the later represents abstract concepts to analyze the phenomenon, such as Prigogine's dissipative structures, Mandelbrot's fractal geometry, chaos theory, catastrophe theory, neural networks and genetic algorithms are. Therefore, emergence may be analyzed by patterns discarding the ontological status and providing a generic view of the phenomenon. In this sense, based on Fromm's taxonomy of emergence (FROMM, 2005), we understand that the first step to contour such vagueness is to define the observation scope of the emergence (BAR-YAM, 2004). Second, to set up strategies to understand the sound event by its interaction properties, in a way that micro and macro levels can be thought of at once: at the micro-level, highlighting the relationships underneath the sound formation through feedback topologies and causal correlations categories; and at the macro-level, listening to the resulting macroform as pattern behaviors based on types of instabilities (SCHMIDT, 2019). Thus, we are focusing on the *interaction qualities* of the system, balancing the organisation of components previously known — which precede interactions — with the characteristics of the emergent patterns we are currently listening to.

3. On the characterization of emergence and the feedback

Jochen Fromm (2005) proposes a classification model of emergent properties based on different types of feedback processes and causal structures, which can also be seen in terms of constrained generating roles, boundaries and hierarchical jumps perspectives (see Table 1). Although it is a very general taxonomy of a highly complex and specific phenomenon, it is very helpful when we need to understand the structure of interactions in a feedback-based musical system.

Based on Fromm's taxonomy it is possible to categorize the emergent phenomenon by its strength. In the *Ecos Study*, it has been used to define the observation scope within the simple and weak types of emergence, disregarding the complexity of the phenomenon when it falls into the cultural field that involves the musical discourse, for example. This approach helps to maintain the objectiveness when dealing with the emergence concept as a structural factor, and to avoid the vagueness in which everything could constitute an emergence.

Type	Name	Character of emergences	Interaction boundaries	Feedback	Hierarchical jumps organization	Common analogies
1	Simple emergence	(1a) Intentional	Agent→system (only one direction)	No feedback but absolute commands or constraints	Static, no jumps	Wave propagation, dominoes effect
		(1b) Unintentional	Agent→agent	Bottom-up causal relations (peer-to-peer)	Fluctuations. No jumps to significant higher level	
2	Weak emergence	(2a) Stable	(Direct actions) agent↔ agent;	Scale-crossing (top-down) negative feedback	Dynamic jumps to higher level	↓
		(2b) Instable	(Indirect actions) agent↔environment	Scale-crossing with prevalent positive feedback		
3	Multiple emergence	(3a) Multiple feedbacks	Agent↔group or agent↔system	Scale-crossing (top-down) with positive and negative feedback	Dynamic jumps to higher level	
		(3b) Adaptative emergences	Large fitness barriers in complex evolutionary systems	Multiple feedbacks in a system	Quantum leap in complex adaptative systems	
4	Strong emergence	independence of macroform structures	Crossing of the barrier of relevance	All of above, including feedback between different systems	Gateway in evolution to new system	The emergence of life and culture

Table 1 - The four types of emergence according to the Fromm’s taxonomy (FROMM, 2005). The type 1b is related with peer-to-peer effects like wave propagation and dominoes effect. On the other extreme, type 4, there is the emergence of life and culture as the strongest type.

By understanding the interaction boundaries and feedback relationships that characterize the typology, it is possible to think in advance what types of emergence the composite system can produce and what types it cannot. In Table 1, the hierarchical jump organisation column illustrates the possible dynamics that can be recognized at the macro level by types of instabilities (SCHMIDT, 2019), whereas the feedback column illustrates possible feedback topologies that organise and constrain the micro level relationships. For instance, the responsiveness of the audible ecosystem to acoustic fluctuations is the basis of its whole behavior profile, starting from the metastability state (PRIGOGINE, 1987) and the Larsen tone formation (AUGOYARD & TORGUE, 2005). These are examples of weak types that can vary from stable to unstable emergence. Any process blocking this behavioral nature will possibly limit the ecosystem to the simple kinds of emergence.

In the *Ecos* model, we are developing control strategies based on controlled feedback topologies and feedback layers (THOMASI & FARIA, 2021, 2022) in order to provoke the emergence of new properties, while preserving the responsiveness to acoustic fluctuations. Nevertheless, it is not a trivial categorization, once it distinguishes audible ecosystems from other feedback-based musical systems. In this sense, categorizing the audible ecosystem’s feedback structure is analogous to categorizing acoustical instruments by their organology.

At the macro level organisation it is possible to distinguish different types of instabilities. Thus, our main tool to deal with such complexity is an analytical listening able to identify the instabilities through sound spectra movements (see Figure 1 and Figure 2). In other words, it is a listening approach focused on the interaction structures behind the sound emergence as an effort to stay below the cultural threshold and restricted to the weak emergence. According to

Schmidt (2019), there are *static* and *dynamical instabilities* that are related to the initial conditions and evolution trajectories, and they can be perceived as natural fluctuations or transitions from one state to another. Transitions are often related with a *structural instability* that mean changes in the model structure itself, also known as *bifurcation* (HOOKER, 2011).

Figure 1 – Illustrative flowchart of the types of instabilities (SCHMIDT, 2019) and bifurcations (HOOKER, 2011). This typology has been useful as a guideline for an analytical listening to patterns of emergence.

Figure 2 – Peak frequency sonogram of the emergent sound spectrum. The number 1-4 points to four different spectral contents generated by changing the feedback topology of the audible ecosystem.

In general terms, there will be a bifurcation if the instability has an impact or is the result of an impact on the structure of the ecosystem. Figure 2 shows a peak-frequency sonogram with spectral transitions that reveals changes in the micro level structure of the ecosystem that causes bifurcations. The segment A shows a bifurcation with low impact in the ecosystem structure. In this case, the dynamical form shifts as a function of the gain parameter, provoking the spectral expansion, but the spectral structure remains constrained to the first harmonic.

By controlling the gain – increasing the feedback-loop energy – it is possible to move along the spectrum. So, this is an irreversible process as far as sound formation is concerned, but the

quality of the emergence can be predictable. In Figure 2, the segment B shows a bifurcation with high impact in the ecosystem structure, since it is the result of a new feedback topology and therefore constitutes a spectral content emerging from a new basis of relations.

4. Final considerations

Based on patterns of emergence we found theoretical support to structurally thinking in the audible ecosystem, drawing attention to the interaction qualities from which the whole ecosystem structure emerges. This approach requires a perspective on sound structures that highlights their dynamics and the relationships behind their formation. This method has supported the *Ecos Study* as a guideline for the implementation of control strategies and also for the elaboration of an ecosystem performance model. In this respect, we could paraphrase Meric and Solomos' question: *what is moving inside what we are listening to?* (MERIC & SOLOMOS, 2014) and start to think *how are they moving inside?*

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